

TRANSFORMATION METHODS OF SEWING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN’S CLOTHES

Khalilova Dildora Jakhongirovna

Assistant, Department Light industry and Textiles, Fergana Polytechnic
Institute, Fergana, Uzbekistan

E-mail: dildorahalilova420@gmail.com.

Abstract: The article will consider the technology of manufacturing transformable clothes for preschoolers. Children’s transformer clothing for preschoolers is in great demand today, as it is multifunctional, eco-friendly and convenient. One piece of clothing can be turned into another, which allows you to create a variety of clothing options in various stylistic solutions, create a unique image and remain stylish in any situation.

Keywords: transformable clothing, multifunctional items, design engineering, clothing transformation method, ecological design.

Introduction

Nowadays, in the process of designing new clothing models, it is necessary to pay attention not only to aesthetic features, but also to provide existing facilities with new features, which, of course, complicates the design process and requires the selection of non-standard engineering solutions. A multifunctional product, a garment made in the style of transformation, can be met as much as possible by adding to the wardrobe products that can perform several functions at the same time or can be turned into other products or assortments without wasting unnecessary time and physical effort.

In this regard, the government has set tasks to increase production, improve the structure of the range of garments, including clothing, improve quality, increase production efficiency through the rapid development of the garment industry [4-5-6].

For the successful implementation of these tasks, the technical reconstruction of enterprises in the garment industry of light industry, the introduction of new complex-mechanized processes, new equipment and advanced technology, the use

of new raw materials, as well as contours of clothing parts, base structures to automate technological processes unification work is required [7-13-17].

Analysis of the literature

During the study of the subject, it can be seen that many leading Uzbek scientists have devoted their research to the design and modeling of clothing, ie the theoretical and practical aspects of sewing in the style of multifunctional products, including S.S. Tashpulatov, M.K. Ramazonova, G.G. Alimova, Sh.G.Juraeva M.Z.Murtazayev, J.Khamidov, G.M.Akhmedova, M.V.Maksimova, M.E.Eshonkulova, K.T. Olimov, T.A. Ochilov, A.T. Trukhanova, M.Sh. Jabborova, M.K.Rasulova, G.K.Kulijonova, S.S.Musayev, O.I.Karimova, The works of G.K. Khasanboyeva, M.Z. Ismatullayeva and others can be singled out [1-2-3].

Research methodology

The following methods and techniques were used in writing the article: systematic and comparative analysis, methods of information processing.

Analysis and results

Transformable clothing is a multi-functional garment that can be converted from one type to another, such as a jacket that turns into a waistcoat, or vice versa. Acquiring and mastering new knowledge, learning a new way of working by learning the same shell and appearance, takes effort and hard work. [9-10-18]. The detachable parts are made by creating a costume design project and using various buttons, zippers, hangers, threads, cords and more. Changing clothes allows you to experiment directly with clothes.

By constantly changing certain details of clothing, a person can create many variants of their clothing in different style solutions, create a unique look, look beautiful in any situation.

The variable model can be used for many years due to its diversity. The use of different modification options in the design of clothing models allows increasing the versatility, expanding their multifunctional capabilities and reducing their purchase costs.

To make the ribbon of products and suppliers more precise, the buyer of changeable clothes actually buys several products with the same material and color combination, but differ in composition and functions. [22] In turn, for the manufacturer, the development and production of garments based on a variable

fabric part is significantly beneficial by saving material, as in this case the waste is minimal [14-15].

Analysis of scientific studies has shown that transformer clothing is popular because its versatility, dynamism and convenience save money and allow you to change your appearance with something. Despite the developments in this field, the creation of different classifications for this type of products, changing clothes is of interest not only to consumers but also to designers. Along with their practicality, the search for new forms is reflected in the development of many fashion houses.

The principle of transformation plays an important role in the formation of a modern theme, including clothing, and provides almost unfinished opportunities for the search for creative solutions of multifunctional forms.

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Under the multifunctional changing wardrobe, there is a single composite integrity and a mobile structure and shape that allows them to complement, replace or transform each other by significantly changing their properties the combined set of evenings is understood.

At the same time, the process of designing new clothing models should focus on not only aesthetic features, but also mainly on providing existing facilities with new features, which, of course, complicates the design process and requires the selection of non-standard engineering solutions.

Modern fashion distinguishes children's clothing in a special direction with its own characteristics. The functions of children's clothing are slightly different from those of adults, the list of which shown in Figure 1.

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Figure 1. Functions of children's clothing

The process of modeling and designing children's clothing is a field of applied art that is developed in conjunction with the main goal of helping to cultivate character and develop the child's aesthetic taste. In the modern world, children have relative independence in choosing their hobbies, style and clothes. At the same time, in the upbringing of a child with an unstable psyche who has not yet been formed, the objects that surround him are part of the fund of educational functions.

According to psychologists, hobbies, firstly, stimulate creative activity, and secondly, bring to life the element of play. This contributes to the development of human thinking skills and, as a result, has a positive effect on basic activities [8-11]. In recent years, one of the main ways to develop a child's thinking has been LEGO constructors. The demand for LEGO technology is primarily due to its high educational potential. During the game, children learn to build and develop motor skills, develop a sequence of actions, plan, and combine colors, shapes, and proportions [20-23].

From a certain age, girls of preschool and primary school age act as fashion designers and start creating clothes for dolls. Through this method of play, the child can not only develop, but also express himself.

In our opinion, the LEGO method of clothing production leads to the development of thinking skills of preschool and primary school children and a constructive approach to problem solving, while the method of sewing should be based on the principle of transformation.

In this case, the LEGO method is an integral part of clothing production and is called modular design. The availability of modules and parts and their installation in various combinations allows you to change the design of some products to others. The modules can be the same size and usually have simple geometric shapes [19 - 20].

Simple flat geometric shapes are used as the main part for preschool and primary school children, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Modules of school uniforms for children

The main module has a rounded square shape, the dimensions of the square are $4 * 4 * 0.1$ see, there is a connecting tongue and two technical holes. An example of connecting modules is shown in Figure 3.

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Figure 3. Module connection method

The modules are available in a variety of color options, which eliminates errors during product installation. In order to make it easier for the child to assemble the product, compared to the “LEGO” and puzzle constructors, in the future the plans for placing the product in the form of pictures can be attached to the modules for assembling clothes. Examples of assembling modules can be offered in black and white, in color, and with a variety of patterns and drawings.

With the modular design method, the school or preschooler is able independently assemble the finished product, such as a jacket, suit, skirt and skirt. The jacket pattern is based on the standard base of a raglan wide jacket. The patterns of the products are shown in Figure 4.

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Figure 4. Shirt sample

Conclusions and suggestions

Thus, the design of the transferable and detachable parts is achieved using various formulas, buttons, hooks, nets, and so on.

When a customer buys a single change of clothes, he or she buys several products that are in fact similar in material and wide range, but differ in range and purpose [12-16]. The manufacturer benefits greatly from the development of garments based on a variable piece of fabric due to efficiency and material savings, as there is almost no waste of material used.

At the same time, the use of modular design based on the principle of transformation in the creation of children's clothing leads to the development of its high educational potential. When creating products from modules and puzzles, children learn to create new things, develop hand motor skills, sequence of movements, color combinations, and proportion analysis.

Clothing with developmental features will help the child to develop into a well-rounded person and will help the child to choose a unique style. It combines educational games, new technologies and expands the scope of the imagination.

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